

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN REGARDING AGE AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE HEALTHY DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHILD

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning yoshga doir psixologik xususiyatlari va ularning bola sog'lom rivojlanishidagi ahamiyatini bilib olishimiz mumkin.

Kalit so'z: bola, mustaqil faoliyat, Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, psixologiya, sog'lom

Аннотация: В этой статье мы можем узнать возрастные психологические особенности дошкольников и их значение для здорового развития ребенка.

Ключевое слово: ребенок, самостоятельная деятельность, дошкольники, психология, здоровье

Annotation: in this article we can find out the psychological characteristics of preschool children regarding age and their importance in the healthy development of the child.

Keyword: child, independent activity, preschool children, psychology, healthy

The preschool age of a child from 3 to 7 years old is a large part of the childhood period. Basically, it is from this period that the child's independent activities develop, and his personal individual characteristics (personal qualities) begin to be composed. From Russian educators P.F.Lesgaft believes that the period of a person's preschool age is such a period during which it is determined what character traits will appear in the future, and the foundations of his moral qualities will arise. On the importance of preschool age in the development of a person's education P.F.This opinion of Lesgaft was expressed by the Russian pedagogue A.S.Fully corresponds to the following opinion of Makarenko. A.S.Makarenko spoke about the need to raise children from a very small period, and the most important foundations of upbringing are laid during the period when the child is under five years old. It was said that the entire upbringing, which was done during this period, accounted for 90% of the upbringing process. Indeed, the period of the child's preschool age is such a meaningful and active period that this period will definitely be reflected in the future growth of the child. Therefore, the period in preschool age is extremely responsible in terms of the power of influence.

When a child passes from the first to the preschool period, serious changes occur in his entire living conditions. First, when the child reaches kindergarten age, his sphere of activity is greatly expanded, and his independence increases even more. His games, his behavior also begin to have a different content. Secondly, the role of speech in the entire activity of the child goes to the Midwest. Thirdly, after preschool age, the child begins to be brought up by a special educator under a certain program. These changes that have arisen in the living conditions of a preschool child will not affect his physical and psychically growing maturation. The physical development of a preschool child as we have already said, the period when a child grows physically fastest falls on the age of one or two years.

After the child turns three years old to preschool age, his physical growth slows down somewhat. Unevenness in the child's physical growth will continue to occur during this period. For example, we can see the increase in height from birth to one year of age in the table below. Indicators of physical development in preschool age: age 0-1 1-2 2-3 3-4 4-5 5-6 6-7 height (cm) 25 40 8 4 6-7 7-8 10 due to the lengthening of the child's body, in particular, legs, the general proportionality in the torso changes. In preschool age, the child's legs grow relatively more. But even so, the bones of a child under 6-7 years old are not yet well hardened, that is, they are in a cartilage state.

The tendons and muscles of preschool children become very mobile, despite the fact that they are not yet strong. When the child reaches the age of 7, there is a certain degree of Flexion in the neck part of the spine towards the front, and in the chest part towards the back. Later, the child's spine is preserved in this form. Of great importance is the fact that the spine is preserved in such a case when the child is straight from Kaddi-Basti. The skull of a child of kindergarten age also grows rapidly. After the child is three years old, the back and top sides of the skull grow rapidly. At preschool age, serious changes also occur in the internal organs of the child. For example, in terms of volume, the child's heart is 4-5 times larger than the baby's heart, but his muscles will not yet be sufficiently strengthened. That is why the heart of a child of kindergarten age cannot squeeze enough blood for the body in one contraction. This is also the reason why a child's heart beats faster than the hearts of older people. Chunonchi, if a child's heart at 1 year old squeezes 10.2 cubic/cm of blood in one contraction, a child's heart at 7 years old will squeeze blood from 23 cubic/cm in one contraction. And the heart of an adult person squeezes more than 60 cubes/ CM of blood in one contraction. Due to the relatively rapid functioning of the heart in

preschool age, the child's blood pressure is slightly stronger than in older people.

Children cannot breathe deeply until their lungs are large enough in size. As a result, children are satisfied with rapid breathing instead of deep breathing. In the period of the child's kindergarten age, the growth of the chest, like other organs, slows down a little. But the expansion of the chest circle continues much faster during this period. The circle of the child's chest expands from 1-2 cm per year, and when he reaches the age of 13-14, he approaches the chest of large people in terms of its shape and size. The amount of breathing of a child in the period from 3 to 7 years old practically does not change. But since during this period the child is overly mobile, his organism requires a huge amount of oxygen. Therefore, the child should be outdoors as much as possible. From these above, we can conclude that by preschool age, the working capacity of his body increases significantly. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly take into account the features of the child's physical development when drawing up educational and educational work in the kindergarten and family, as well as the regime of the child's activity. The growth of the nervous system of preschool children a huge role in the development of the psyche of preschool children is played by the changes that occur in their nervous systems. The strongest progressing period of the children's nervous systems falls on the period under 1 year of age. The average weight of the brain of a newborn child comes 380-400 g. Until the child reaches kindergarten age, his brain develops incredibly quickly and increases almost three times.

Hence, the weight of the brain of children who have reached kindergarten age reaches 1100-1200 g. During the further improvement of the nervous system of preschool children, nerve fibers that connect the Centers in the cerebral cortex with each other also begin to be covered with myelin sheaths. The lining of nerve fibers in the brain with myelin sheaths is of great importance for the process of reflection, that is, for psychic processes and their development. When nerve fibers are myelinated, firstly, the rapid passage of excitations through the nerve fibers is ensured, and secondly, it ensures that excitation only goes to the corresponding Center. This results in a relatively rapid formation of conditioned reflexes (temporal bonds), which occur due to the action of various pathogens that affect the body from the external environment. In addition, the precise course of each excitation to the respective center ensures that kindergarten-age children can handle their movements with agility.

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